

CRITICAL STUDY OF PADMA SHRI AWARDEE JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR- INDIAN ATHLETE

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ABSTRACT:

Traditional and prominent sporting events, such as the Olympic Games, recognise the significance of physical agility and skill, while other organisations, such as the Olympic Council of Asia, use definitions to exclude any activity that does not involve physical exertion from its roster of sanctioned sports. Whatever the case may be, confirmation as a mental sport has massive numbers of serious, inactive attesters. Anyone who participates in athletic events, track and field competitions, or other forms of organised sports is considered an athlete. After stepping down, many elite athletes believe it's difficult, if not impossible, to find genuine again. This research study aims to examine the life, career, and accolades of Padma Shri Awardee Jyotirmoyee Sikdar, an Indian athlete.

KEYWORDS: Athlete, sports, games, achievement, physical, arrangement , award

INTRODUCTION:

Traditional and prominent sporting events, such as the Olympic Games, recognise the significance of physical agility and skill, while other organisations, such as the Olympic Council of Asia, use definitions to exclude any activity that does not involve physical exertion from its roster of sanctioned sports. Whatever the case may be, confirmation as a mental sport has massive numbers of serious, inactive attesters. Even though there

aren't many activities that use the mind or brain, the International Olympic Committee has acknowledged chess and scaffolding as sports, along with the other five non-physical sports recognised by the World Sports Federation and Association. People in charge of sports include

set of rules and conventions, those that guide to ensure fair competition, to allow consistent declaration of winner or victor. The authorities would choose the winner based on how well the players perform in the game, whether that's in terms of scoring points, reaching the end goal first, covering the most distance in the least amount of time, or throwing objects, like a shot put, for a greater distance than the other competitor. Sports may be defined as an all-encompassing kind of physical and mental growth that, with the help of either a casual or formal commitment, involves pushing oneself to one's physical and mental limits, building social connections, and reaping the benefits of competition at various levels.

This Indian politician and athlete was called Jyotirmoyee Sikdar. Back in the 14th Lok Sabha, she represented West Bengal's Krishnagar seat as a member of parliament. As a Marxist, she is a member of the Communist Party of India. Even in the 2009 Lok Sabha

election, she ran for the Krishnanagar seat, but she was unsuccessful in her

attempt to get a second term in office.

She won the 800 metre race at the Asian Athletics Championships in 1995 while competing in the middle distance. She continued her winning ways in 1998, taking home bronze in the 800 m and gold in the 1500 m races at the Asian Athletics Championships in Bangkok.

Bollywood actress and former athlete Jyotirmoyee Sikdar was born on December 11, 1969, in India. She represented the Krishnagar seat in the fourteenth Lok Sabha as a member of the Communist Party of India (Marxist), however in the 2009 Indian general election, she was soundly defeated by Trinamool Congress actor-turned-politician Tapas Paul. It was said that after her beating, she had been politically dormant. In 2019, she committed her support to the All India Trinamool Congress before joining the Bharatiya Janata Party.

Born to Gurudas and Nihar Sikdar in Debagram, Nadia area, West Bengal, on December 11, 1969, Sikdar attended school until high school. On February 9, 1994, Sikdar

tied the knot with Avtar Singh, and they are parents.

Today, 51-year-old Sikdar received the saffron flag from West Bengal State President Dilip Ghosh and participated in Union Home Minister Amit Shah's virtual convention with the people of West Bengal.

He was a middle distance runner for India in the mid-1990s and won many championships, including gold at the Asian Athletics Championships in 1998 and the Asian Games in Bangkok in 1998. In 2004, he entered politics and won a parliamentary seat from Krishnanagar on the Marxist platform CPI(M). She then defeated Satyabrata Mukherjee, a BJP candidate and the Union Minister of Chemicals and Fertilisers.

Subhas Chakraborty, the previous minister of sports, had Sikdar as his assistant. During the 2016 Assembly election, she was a member of the CPI(M) campaign. Nevertheless, she was defeated by the late Tapas Pal, a Tollywood star and relative newcomer, in the following

2009 parliamentary poll.

Achievements:

Year	Competition	Venue	Position	Notes
Representing India				
1998	Asian Championships	Fukuoka, Japan	3rd	800 m
			3rd	1500 m
	Asian Games	Bangkok, Thailand	1st	800 m
			1st	1500 m

“Jyotirmoyee Sikdar has been an Indian Athlete and has brought the nation laurels by grabbing Gold Medals at Bangkok Asian Games 1998”.

“She was born on the 11th of December 1969 at Debagram, a small town in the Nadia district of West Bengal. Jyotirmoyee had Athletics and sports spirit running in her veins as her father had himself been a former Pole Vaulter. She made her tryst with Athletics at a very

young age, and Satyaram Roy, her mentor spotted her immense talent quite soon”.

1.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To discuss the biography, early life of Padma Shri Awardee Jyotirmoyee Sikdar.
2. To study the achievements and awards of the Jyotirmoyee Sikdar
3. To assess the political and sports career of the Jyotirmoyee Sikdar

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW:

Kumar and Shirotriya, Awadhesh (2019) A well-thought-out sports plan is the bedrock of every successful sporting endeavour. The display, as measured by the number of decorations at various international athletic events, has been positively impacted by the sports policies of European countries and China. The tremendous enthusiasm and boundless energy of Indian competitors is undeniably a major factor in the meteoric rise

of Indian sports. Despite having the world's second-largest population, India has struggled to bring home Olympic medals since 1900. A lack of engaging sports strategy might be the related underlying motivation, however there are many more answers to the question. An inspiring desire to make a lasting impression in the 2020 Tokyo Olympics has been sparked by the consistently remarkable performance of Indian athletes in Asian events. Regular reviews of the sports policy are necessary. We

should adopt the Chinese approach in this case. With each approaching Olympic Games, China modifies its sports policy. It is important that our players and coaches are aware of the resources available to them in terms of sports strategy. To that end, the administration should periodically host workshops and organise public level courses and gatherings focused on sports strategy. We would also appreciate any suggestions for ways to assess the effectiveness of sports strategy work so that we can incorporate changes to specific goals into future plans.

Singh, Choudhary, and Shilpa (2019): The term "somatotyping" refers to a system that uses three numerical ratings to describe an individual's morphology and structure. When it comes to identifying talented athletes and developing training programmes, anthropometry and somatotype are often used. 165 elite Indian athletes from football, wrestling, hockey, combat sports, and athletics, together with 18 members of the benchmark group, were somatotyped using the method developed by Heath and Carter. We used the guidelines established by the International Society for the Advancement of Kinanthropometry for our anthropometric measurements. When compared to the benchmark group, the examined groups were quite dissimilar from one another, and within each group, inconsistency was reduced. Participants in the study exhibited more endomorphy or ectomorphy and lower mesomorphs when compared to Olympic athletes.

Sharma, Gandhi, and Gursatej (2019) "Clinical practice" typically acknowledges the beneficial consequences of physical exercise on overall prosperity, leisure goals, and professional performance, which have long been the

justifications for participating in traditional sports. Concentrated exercise may increase oxidative stress and perhaps cause genetic damage, according to some evidence. Differential acceptance of oxidative stress and induction of oxidation of cell macromolecules (including DNA) and cell brokenness can occur depending on the power, time, frequency, and qualities of activities. On the one hand, this can accumulate with age and physical properties, increasing susceptibility to illness. On the other hand, it can activate cell flagging pathways, leading to cell variation and improved stress protection. The effects on oxidative/cancer prevention agent alterations and DNA damage in skilled Kho players adjusted by individual genetic differences were studied to determine whether continuous sports activities, such as Kho, increase oxidation limit, which may also stimulate oxidation of cell macromolecules. Game of 'Tag' with traditional Indian roots, Kho is one of the most popular sports in the world and a true test of skill, agility, and determination. The healthy Kho players (20.27 ± 0.28 y; sports age 6.78 ± 0.52 y) and controls (20.90 ± 0.45 y) were matched for age, sex, body mass index (BMI), maximal oxygen uptake (VO_2 max), occurrence of GSTT1 (present/invalid), M1 (present/invalid), and SOD2 (C199T) polymorphisms, but they differed for variation allele frequencies of GSTP1 (A313G) and SOD2 (C47T). The levels of DNA damage, lipid peroxidation, and absolute cell reinforcement were significantly higher in players compared to controls. However, there were no differences in SOD movement, lipid peroxidation, or absolute cell reinforcement. Due to the similarity in the study group's other features, these results suggest that the players had increased genetic damage and oxidative stress, perhaps as a result of the intense

physical activity without other exposures. As a result, athletes should be alert to the health risks associated with regular, intense physical activity, as they may be more vulnerable to cancer, other illnesses, and the effects of ageing.

Gomathinayagam, Josephin, and Arulmozhi S. (2019) Sport and the host purpose may be used to promote the experiences that game voyagers acquire, which in turn advances the travel sector. Consequently, there is room for improvement in the game-movement industry across a variety of forms (spectating, sharing, enjoying game locations), and the concept of establishment and organisations at the target provide crucial support to the whole game-movement industry experience. The impact of sport travellers may be greatly enhanced by providing them with opportunities to engage with like-minded other travellers. When pleasure and the development company's suppliers form their interests vertically and evenly, they participate in cross-using of redirection and aims. Investigating the social and mental worlds of redirection travellers and identifying persuasive frameworks need more research.

In 2019, Mong, Hanne, and Standal Recent years have seen a proliferation of research focusing on the role of physical education (PE) in promoting health. There are a variety of perspectives on the importance of health in physical education, and this research recalls discussions on different perspectives. Few studies have focused on finding the optimal approach to health education, although there are reasons to acknowledge that different health pedagogical approaches will provide

different results. Assessment rationale and strategy: In order to better understand how physical education (PE) teachers teach health, this article will conduct a writing audit. Sport Discuss, ERIC, and ISI Web of Science were the three independent databases that the writing search relied on. After the ban cycle, we only managed to collect 30 of the 1903 pieces we found. The writing is examined using the instructional triangle, a hypothetical approach proposed by Gudem (2011). Results: Results demonstrate that students' understanding of health, the methods used to present the topic, and the roles played by teachers and students vary significantly between the biomedical and elective perspectives on health. The research shows that different schools of thought on health place an emphasis on different approaches to health education in physical education. To conclude, this study has investigated the potential pedagogical effects of several approaches to health in physical education. The differences between the biomedical and elective approaches to physical education (PE) and their respective views on the nature of health, the roles of the instructor, and the students have been illuminated via the use of a didactical methodology.

"Quennerstedt and Mikael" (2019) The José María Cagigal Scholar Lecture, which was presented during the 2018 AIESEP World Congress in Edinburgh, is used in this study. In the study, I argue that greater physical education, where many ways of living on this planet as an individual are both possible and empowered, is the major real achievable emphasis on PE. In order to get here, we must focus on the field of teaching as a means of critically analysing and developing innovative, broadly inclusive physical education

programmes. To do this, I look at education through the lens of its pedagogical function, a particular viewpoint on the student, and teaching as an ongoing display of decision-making about the what, why, and how of education, governing choices regarding enticing change. I. Getting back to a student-centered view of education; (ii) reclaiming PE's expansive nature; and (iii) reclaiming PE teachers' expertise—which is closely related to being an educator and deciding what to bring to the classroom—are all important takeaways. Before we can even think about "the how" and "what," we need to know "the why" of education.

3.0 PADMA SHRI AND ARJUNA AWARDS

3.1 OVERVIEW

The Padma Vibhushan, Padma Bhushan, and Padma Shri are the three most distinguished civilian awards bestowed by the Indian government. Various orders/fields of exercise are recognised with awards, such as: craftsmanship, social work, public undertakings, science and design, exchange and industry, medicine, writing and training, sports, common help, etc. The 'Padma Vibhushan' is given for outstanding and recognised service, the 'Padma Bhushan' for

distinguished service of high order, and the 'Padma Shri' for distinguished service in any realm. Republic Day is the annual occasion on which the honours are announced. The President of India bestows these honours in solemn ceremonies conducted annually at Rashtrapati Bhawan, usually in the springtime. Here is a rundown of all 141 Padma Awards that the president has approved this year, including four couple instances (the Award is counted as one in a team case). Included in the list are 118 Padma Shri Awards, 7 Padma Vibhushan, and 16 Padma Bhushan. Of the total number of awards, 33 are women. The list also includes 18 individuals from the category of Foreigners/NRI/PIO/OCI and 12 who were honoured after death. The following is a list of the 141 Padma Awards that the president has approved for presentation this year; in four of these instances, the honour was shared between members of a team. The list includes 118 Padma Shri Awards, 7 Padma Vibhushan, and 16 Padma Bhushan. A total of 36 individuals have been honoured with these accolades; among them are 33 women, 18 members of the category of Foreigners/NRI/PIO/OCI, and 12 recipients who have passed away.

3.2 PADMA AWARDS

The Padma Awards, which have been going strong since 1954, are traditionally announced on Republic Day every year with the exception of two short breaks in 1978 and 1979 and 1993–1997.

There are three categories into which the prize is bestowed:

Three Padma Awards: the Padma Vibhushan for outstanding and acknowledged service, the Padma Bhushan for acknowledged service to a high request, and the Padma Shri for acknowledged service.

No one is denied eligibility for these prizes because of their gender, colour, or place of employment. However, save for experts and researchers, no government employee, including those employed by PSUs, is eligible to receive these Awards.

"Recognised and outstanding accomplishments/administration in all fields of exercises/disciplines" are celebrated with this award, which seeks to recognise works of qualification. Here is a summary of the fields to help you understand them:

- Art (which includes performing arts, visual arts, architecture, film, and more)
- Social work (which encompasses all forms of

charitable aid, social service, involvement in community projects, and similar endeavours)

- Politics, Law, and Public Life (Commonly Known as "Public Affairs").

Space engineering, nuclear science, IT, R&D in science and related fields, etc. all fall under the umbrella of "science and engineering."

- Commerce and Industry (which includes Financial Services, Management, Economic Operations, Tourism Promotion, and Business, among other things)

The medical field (which includes conventional and alternative medicine, homoeopathy, naturopathy, Ayurveda, Sidhha, and other sub-disciplines)

- Literature and Education (which encompasses fields such as journalism, education, bookmaking, literature, poetry, and the advocacy of better teaching practices, higher standards of competency, and educational reforms)
- Civil service (which includes government employees' qualifications, organisational excellence, etc.)
- Sports (including all forms of athletics, adventure sports, mountaineering, sports innovation, yoga, and so on)
- Other (not mentioned above) (e.g., areas concerned with protecting human rights, ensuring the survival of endangered species, promoting Indian culture, etc.)

3.2.1 HISTORY, SIGNIFICANCE & DETERMINATION OF ALL ABOUT PADMA AWARDS:

The "Bharat Ratna" and the "Padma Vibhushan" were two major civilian honours bestowed by the Indian government in 1954. Sri Lanka's highest civilian honour, the Bharat Ratna, and its second-highest civilian honour, the Padma Vibhushan, both belong to nonmilitary persons.

Pahela Varg, Dusra Varg, and Teesra Varg were the three divisions that followed in Padma Vibhushan's classification. Subsequently, each of these categories was rechristened as Padma Vibhushan, Padma Bhushan, or Padma Shree.

Discrimination based on gender, race, profession, or status is nonexistent. The award's criteria include "administration in any field including administration delivered by Government workers" (i.e., experts and researchers), but do not apply to individuals involved in public-area projects.

The announcement of Padma Awards in these three categories takes place annually on January 26th, Republic Day. The total number of prizes that may be granted each year should not exceed 120, excluding honours given after death and to non-resident Indians, foreigners, and OCIs.

During the extended period of March or April, the President of India often bestows the honour. The recipients are presented with an insignia and a Sanad, which means endorsement, from the President.

The President of India has approved the 2017 Padma Award ceremony, which will honour 89 individuals: 7 with the Padma Vibhushan, 7 with the Padma Bhushan, and 75 with the Padma Shri. A total of 19 females, 5 non-resident Indians, 1 person from a PIO category, and 6 posthumous winners make up this list of honorees.

PADMA VIBHUSHAN - SECOND HIGHEST CIVILIAN AWARD OF

INDIA

The Padma Vibhushan is the second-highest civilian honour in India, after the Bharat Ratna. The presentation took place on January 2, 1954. To recognise "exceptional and distinguished service," the prize was established.

The 2017 Padma Vibhushan Award went to seven deserving individuals.

3.3 TYPES OF PADMA AWARDS

3.3.1 PADMA VIBHUSHAN

- Teejan Bai of Chattisgarh for Folk, Art, and Vocal Performance. The people of Chhattisgarh listen to her folk songs.
- Djiboutian Foreigner Ismail Omar Guellah (for public affairs). Since 1999, he has served as the leader of Djibouti.
- The Maharashtra Secretary for Trade and

Industry, Anilkumar Manibhai Naik. He heads the project firm Larsen and Tubro as its chief executive officer.

This is Balwant Moreshwar Purandare from Maharashtra's acting theatre. He is well-known as a Maharashtra theatre actor.

3.3.2 PADMA BHUSHAN

- This prize, which includes the mountaineer Bachendri Pal of Uttarakhand, is one of fourteen that have been announced. Among Indian women, she is the first to reach the summit of Mount Everest.
- Former Indian prime minister Hukumdev Narayan Yadav and BJP lawmaker from Madhubani, Bihar, tasked with handling public affairs.
- Kali Munda, a former vice chairman of the Rajya Sabha from Jharkhand, for public affairs;
- Kuldip Nayyar, a renowned columnist and basic novelist from Delhi, for writing and news coverage after death.

3.3.3 PADMA SHRI

Ninety-four people have been announced as recipients of the Padma Shri award. Some examples include the following: Rajeshwar Acharya, artist Jyoti Bhatt, footballer Sunil Chhetri, and actor Manoj Bajpayee.

Dancer Nartaki Natraj from Tamil Nadu becomes the first transgender person to get the Padma Shri honour.

3.3.4 RECIPIENTS OF ARJUNA AWARD

There were a total of 147 prizes presented in the 1990s: thirteen in 1990, seven in 1991, ten in 1993, eight in 1994, nine in 1995, eighteen in 1996, twenty-one in 1997, thirty in 1998, and twenty-three in 1999. Among the 29 sports represented, there were 21 from hockey, 20 from athletics, 11 from kabaddi, 9 from boxing, cricket, shooting, and weightlifting, 8 from wrestling, 4 from badminton, golf, judo, grass tennis, paddling, swimming, and yachting, 3 from table tennis and volleyball, 2 from arrow based weaponry, football, and squash,

and one from each of the following sports: kho kho, powerlifting, equestrian, chess, carrom, billiards, snooker, and b-ball. One of the most notable recipients was Leander Paes, who was honoured in 1990 and is widely considered one of the best doubles players in tennis history. He was a Grand Slam doubles champion eight times and a blended doubles champion 10 times. As the first Indian person to earn an Olympic medal since 1952,

he was also the first to win a bronze medal in men's single tennis at the 1996 Paris Olympics. As stated in the Encyclopaedia Britannica, Sachin Tendulkar is one of the greatest batters of all time. He became the first batsman to reach 100 centuries in international competition, and he received the accolade in 1994. In 2014, he became the first sportsperson to get the Bharat Ratna, India's highest civilian honour, and he also holds the record for most runs scored in international cricket. Hockey player and Indian public group commander Dhanraj Pillay (awarded in 1995). With 300 and 39 appearances for the public group and 70 goals, he is considered one of the top Indian players, everything else being equal. Rahul Dravid, another batsman, was honoured in 1998. He is known as The Wall because to "the feeling of perpetual quality to be found in his batting." Dravid is considered one of the best batters of all time and the fourth highest run-scorer in Test cricket.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

4.1 Research Methodology:

A systematic approach to a problem is known as research methodology. Research methodology is the focus here. Research methodology refers to the general frameworks that scientists use to describe, explain, and predict the outcomes of their investigations. It is also defined as the study of information retrieval techniques. Its purpose is to lay forth a strategy for doing research.

4.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

To explore a rational problem efficiently, researchers use research designs. Research

questions, hypotheses, free and ward factors, trial design, information gathering methods, and a quantifiable examination plan are all aspects of a study's design, which in turn defines the study's type (e.g., illuminating longitudinal contextual investigation), as well as its trial, survey, and meta-logical components. A research design is a predetermined plan for gathering data and analysing it.

4.2.1 DESIGN TYPES AND SUB-TYPES

The qualification is sometimes fake, and other times several designs are combined, however there are a lot of ways to organise research designs. Whatever the situation may be, the following list provides a number of helpful distinctions between potential study strategies.

4.3 SELECTION OF SUBJECTS:

A fundamental role in the trial design is the selection of the appropriate member population. Of the three pillars upon which the research design rests, the research topic stands tallest. Accurately selecting study participants is critical to the success of the investigation. This topic was selected with JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR's (PADMASHREE AWARDEE) dedication to Indian athletics in mind.

4.3.1 SELECTION OF THE INSTRUMENTS

A crucial step in the research process is choosing the tools that will be used to gather data. At this point, you should have a system in place to ensure that the data you've gathered is legitimate and trustworthy, and most importantly, that it will be comparable to what you anticipate.

An suitable survey will be developed as part of the study technique to gather the necessary data pertaining to Jyotirmoyee Sikdar's life and achievements. Data analysis will also take place.

4.4 DATA COLLECTION

Research is a unique activity that goes beyond just gathering information or writing an account. It entails collecting data in a targeted manner and then analysing it thoroughly to answer research questions and evaluate outcomes. Regardless of the area of study, data gathering is fundamental to research designs. The first step of every research project is to formulate a set of questions. To gather appealing data for a social event in a careful and distortion-free manner is the first step in doing an analysis that will hopefully provide reasonable and credible results.

Here, we shall analyse all the relevant data of Jyotirmoyee Sikdar in order to acquire the result. The suggested technique is case study analysis.

4.4.1 TYPES OF DATA

There are two types of data

- **Primary Data**

The data accumulated by researcher directly is primary data. The researcher collects such data intentionally, on the grounds that no past records of the data

exist to be gotten to by open. Primary data can be collected utilizing a scope of methods like overviews, interviews, center gatherings, and so forth Such data is viewed as exceptionally solid.

The fundamental unit of a Case Study is a Case. It is a specific study. A Case Study might be founded on a person, a gathering of people, a country, a race, a specific class of a people, networks and organizations, which are treated as a unit as a unit of analysis and enlightening report of the status of an individual subject as for her character. The fundamental system of the Case Study method is to assess all appropriate parts of a certain something or circumstance, utilizing as the unit for study; an individual, a foundation, a network or any gathering considered as a unit.

- **Secondary Data**

Secondary data are statistics that have already been compiled and approved by an authority figure and are thus accessible to the public at large. This information is derived by the expert from several sources, including previous tests. The data that is gathered for one study and then used for another study is called secondary data. Secondary data often consists of things like government reports, census data, records from various departments, and so on. It's faster and cheaper to use this data than original data.

Secondary Data: In addition to the primary

materials already stated, secondary sources such as current and former players, coaches, directors, umpires, and families were also consulted.

4.5 DELIMITATIONS

Researchers should cite their delimitations, which are their choices. They show the boundaries you've established for the research.

The research is limited in the following ways:

1. Jyotirmoyee Sikdar, "Indian athlete" and recipient of the Padma Shri award, was the only subject of the research.
2. In his career, Padma Shri Jyotimoyee Sikdar will focus on his initiative qualities.
3. His character will serve as the boundary for the investigation.
4. He will be introduced to the world and the study will span the era up to the present.

4.6 LIMITATIONS

Constraints are effects over which the researcher has no control. These are the researcher-involved shortcomings, situations, or influences that restrict your methods and outcomes.

Since this study will rely on information provided by the athletic department, in addition to secondary sources, for its data collection needs.

- 1) The researcher should consult primary and secondary materials, including interviews with Jyotirmoyee Sikdar, his family, friends, coaches, teammates, teammates' friends, instructors, and other key individuals who may have knowledge on the issue that has not been previously studied. Websites, sports publications, newspapers, and

site pages were further sources of data collection; however, each of these sources has its own limits.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 INTRODUCTION:

This section of the research paper examines Jyotirmoyee Sikdar, including her biography, childhood, sports career, political career, awards, and accomplishments. It also discusses Jyotirmoyee's appearances in Jyotirmoyee

Figure 5.2 Jyotirmoyee Sikdar

Indian politician and former athlete Jyotirmoyee Sikdar was born on December 11, 1969. She was a member of the fourteenth Lok Sabha representing the Krishnagar constituency as an independent member of the Communist Party of India (Marxist). Tapas Paul, a former comedian and current politician for the Trinamool Congress, defeated her in the 2009 Indian general election. After her demise, she supposedly did nothing about governmental matters. After everything was said and done in 2019, she eventually joined the Bharatiya Janata Party after pledging assistance to the everything India Trinamool Congress. Her triumph in the 800 metre race at the 1995 Asian Athletics Championships showcased her middle-distance running prowess. After that, in 1998, she went on to win gold in the 800 m and 1500 m events at the Asian Games in Bangkok, as well as bronze in the Asian Athletics Championships.

steals the show and interviews with Rediff and TOI, respectively.

5.2 JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR

An Indian athlete named Jyotirmoyee Sikdar brought honour to her nation in 1998 at the Asian Games in Bangkok with a pair of gold medals. Afterwards, she shifted her focus to legislative matters and became an effective politician after being elected to the Lok Sabha from the Krishnagar constituency in West Bengal in 2004 on the Communist Party of India slate.

In 1995, she received the Arjuna Award, and in 1998–1999, she was honoured with the Rajiv Gandhi Khel Ratna award. In 2003, she was awarded the Padma Shri. My life Sikdar was born to Gurudas and Nihar Sikdar in the West Bengali village of Debagram in the Nadia area on December 11, 1969. At the age of eighteen, she had finished high school and was enlisted in the railroads. She was offered a job chance by railroads after she won the All India varsity games. Avrajyoti Singh, Sikdar's daughter with husband Avtar Singh, is also a rifle shooting medalist; the couple wed on February 9, 1994. During the Olympics in Atlanta and the World Championship in Sweden, Jyotirmoyee addressed the Indian audience. She keeps her athletic spirit alive by contributing to the Athletic Federation of India's Executive Committee. She is talented in the kitchen and the garden, in addition to her athletic abilities. She generously shares the

bounty of her kitchen garden with those she loves, which includes a wide variety of homegrown delicacies. Many people's favourite tree is the mango tree. She feels strongly about topics related to network effort and the empowerment of women. She is a former member of the House of Representatives' Rural Development and Human Resources Joint Committees.

For 1998–1999, she was honoured with the Rajiv Gandhi Khel Ratna. In 2003, she was awarded the Padma Shri. Speaking to Railways, Asian superstar and national record holder Luka protected her title with a mild 2:01.84, bettering the 18-year-old meet record of 2:02.28 established by Jyotirmoyee Sikdar.

5.2.1 EARLY LIFE OF JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR

She was born on December 11, 1969, in the sleepy town of Debagram in West Bengal's Nadia area. Because her father had been a pole vaulter in the past, Jyotirmoyee inherited a passion for athletics and a love of sports. Her mentor, Satyaram Roy, saw her enormous potential shortly after she had her first experience with athletics when she was very young.

5.2.2 BIOGRAPHY OF JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR

Jyotirmoyee Sikdar was born in 1969 in Debogram Village, Nadia District, West Bengal. His family hails from the same region. Her guru Satyaram Roy saw her when she was very young. After making her debut in the 1992 All India Open Meet, when she won silver in the 800-meter event, she became a popular figure in the world of athletics. She turned things around in 1994 by setting yet another world record and taking home the gold medal in the 1500-meter event at the National

Athletics Meet. Jyotirmoyee Sikdar, who is now a member of parliament, was formerly one of the best athletes in the country. She took home the first prize in the 1995 Asian Track & Field Championships in Jakarta, Indonesia. She was awarded the Rajiv Gandhi Khel Ratna for 1998–99 for her dedication to Indian Athletics. After undergoing more training in Germany, she won the gold medal in the 800 metres and 1500 metres events in the 1998 Asian Games, proving once again how brilliant she was. Upon Jyotirmoyee's triumphant return to Kolkata, a large number of people were there at the airport to greet her. She had to give up sports and her career prematurely due to a significant health problem. After running on a platform of legislative reform, she was elected to the Lok Sabha in 2004.

Bengali lawmaker Jyotirmoyee Sikdar is a former rival. Born on December 11, 1969, in the town of Debogram in the Nadia area of West Bengal, Jyotirmoyee began her athletic career as a worthy runner-up to Shiny Abraham in the 800 metres, but she quickly expanded her sphere of influence to include the 400 and 1,500 metres as well. While earning her degree in physiology, she worked on her endurance with the help of her dad, a former shaft vaulter, by running through the fields.

In 1992, Jyotirmoyee made her grand entrance in the All-India Open Meet, when she won silver in the 800 metre event. She earned a spot at the 1993 South Asian Federation (SAF) Games in Dhaka, Bangladesh, where she finished second in the 1,500-meter race, after winning the Open Nationals the previous year. After winning gold in the 1993 Singapore Open, she went on to make history in the 1,500-meter race at the 1994 National

Athletics Meet. She qualified for the 1994 Asian Games in Hiroshima by going under Shiny Abraham's 800-meter record in the preliminary events. She competed in the 1,500-meter event on two times but could only manage fourth place. In 1994, she competed at the World Railways Meet in London as part of the 4x400m transfer team that took home the gold medal. At the 1995 Asian Track and Field Meet in Jakarta, she raced the 800 metres and helped her team win silver in the 4x400m relay. She had previously competed at the World Championships in Sweden. The same year she won gold in the 400 metres in Taipei and was a member of the Indian 4x400m hand-off squad at the Atlanta Olympics, she also set a new public record in the 800 metres in 1995. In 1996, she was also awarded Indian Railways Best Sports person. Her medal haul at the International 1TC Meet included a bronze in 1994 and two golds and a silver in 1997, her two seasons of competing. At the 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok, where she boosted national morale, shook members' confidence, and silenced media criticism of sports officials, Jyotirmoyee Sikdar won two gold medals and a silver medal. The 'New Golden Girl' of India, a 29-year-old contestant, was once again bestowed the title. She won Samsung's "Most Valued Performance Award" in 1995, making her effectively an Arjuna Award winner. She became the leading contender for the Rajiv Gandhi Khel Ratna Award few years later (1998).

5.3 JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR'S CAREER IN SPORTS

5.3.1 JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR AS NATIONAL ATHLETICS

It was during the 1992 All India Open Meet that Sikdar first gained widespread attention for her stellar performance in national athletics. She found out how to steal second place in the 800 metre run in her first public level athletic competition in what seemed like an eternity. Gold was Jyotirmoyee's reward in the 1993 Open National Athletics Meet, which took place the next year. She set yet another national record and took home the gold medal in the 1500-meter event at the 1994 National Athletics Meet. In addition, her 1995 800-meter run set yet another national record.

5.3.2 JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR AS INTERNATIONAL ATHLETICS

- 2 In 1993, in the Dhaka South Asian Federation (SAF) Games, Jyotirmoyee made her international debut by winning silver in the 1500m event. In addition, she won the gold medal in the 1993 Singapore Open Athletics Championship, which was a comparable event. She managed to finish fourth in the 1,500-meter event in the 1994 Hiroshima Asian Games, and she even beat Shiny Abraham's preparation in the 800-meter event at the Trials for the Asian Games. Additionally, in the 1994 World Railway Meet in London, Jyotirmoyee competed in the 4x400 multi stage sprint and came away with a gold medal. She attended a brief training session in Germany as she was interested in a competition overseas, and she showed improvement in the middle distance races. At the Asian Track and Field Meet in Jakarta in 1995, she not only competed in the 800 m and 4x400 m multi-stage sprint events, but she also participated in the World Athletics Championship in Sweden. During the 1996 Atlanta Olympics, she competed in the 4x400 relay and brought home the gold medal in the 400m event in the Taipei Games. She received the title of Best

Sportsperson of the Year 1996 from the Indian Railways. During his two appearances at the International ITC Athletics Meet, Sikdar won bronze in 1994 and a pair of medals in 1997. She competed in the 1997 Asian Track and Field Meet in Fukoka, Japan, and brought home bronze medals in the 800-meter and 1500-meter events, as well as silver in the 4x400-meter relay. At the 1998 Bangkok Asian Games, Jyotirmoyee showcased her profession to the best of her ability by setting two world records in the 800 metre run (2 minutes, 1.0 seconds) and the 1500 metre run (4 minutes, 28.82 seconds). In addition to winning a silver medal in the 4x400 hand-off event, she also earned a gold medal in both of these other competitions.

1.1 POLITICAL CAREER OF JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR

Jyotirmoyee Sikdar jumped into politics in 2004 while still a member of the Communist Party of India (Marxist) (CPI-M), after a successful career as an accomplished Indian athlete. She ran for the fourteenth Lok Sabha in 2004 from West Bengal's Krishnagar Lok Sabha Constituency on a CPI-M ticket and was successful both electorally and politically, defeating BJP candidate Satyabrata Mookherjee with 3,97,561 votes. Former CPI(M) member and Asian Games gold medalist Jyotirmoyee Sikdar has joined the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) after finding inspiration in Prime Minister Narendra Modi's Savka Saath Savka Vikash programme.

Sikdar, who is 51 years old, received the saffron flag from West Bengal's president, Dilip Ghosh, and participated in Union Home Minister Amit Shah's virtual convention with the people of West Bengal today.

Turned political in 2004 and won a parliamentary seat from Krishnagar on the Marxist ticket CPI(M). He was a former middle-distance runner in the mid-1990s who won many accolades for India, including the Asian Athletics Championships in 1998 and gold medals in both the 1998 and 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok. This is when she decisively defeated Satyabrata Mukherjee, a rising star in the BJP and the Union Minister of Chemicals and Fertilisers. Former Sports Minister Subhas Chakraborty has a close relationship with Sikdar. She had been an active member of the CPI(M)'s 2016 Assembly campaign. Regardless, the subsequent 2009 parliamentary poll saw her defeated by the late Tapas Pal, a Tollywood celebrity and relative political newcomer. Following her humiliation, she acted irrationally politically until May 2019, when she reemerged as a member of the ruling Trinamool Congress. She went on to say that Chief Minister Mamata Banerjee's reforms in Bengal had a magnetic hold on her. However, she was likely waiting for the go-ahead when she hosted state BJP president Dilip Ghosh at her house last weekend and presented her with a pink lotus flower.

1.2 JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR'S AWARDS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

In 1995, Jyotirmoyee Sikdar was presented with an Arjuna Award by the Government of India. This award was given to her in recognition of her outstanding performance as a sportsperson on both the national and international stages, as well as her dedication to her country, which she demonstrated on multiple occasions. The Rajiv Gandhi Khel Ratna, India's highest sporting honour, was bestowed to her in 1998 furthermore. Only Sikdar was the primary athlete to get this prestigious accolade.

Figure 5.3: Jyotirmoyee Sikdar honoured

1.2.1 ACHIEVEMENTS OF JYOTIRMOYEE SIKDAR

- Won first place in the 800-meter race at the 1995 Asian Track & Field Championships in Jakarta
- Two 800-meter and 1500-meter gold medals at the 1998 Asian Games

Award for 1998–1999: the Rajiv Gandhi Khel Ratna

YEAR	EVENT	COMPETITION	AWARDS
1995	800 METERS	ASIAN TRACK AND FIELD MEET, JAKARTA	GOLD MEDAL
1998	800 METERS	ASIAN GAMES, BANGKOK	GOLD MEDAL
1998	1500 METERS	ASIAN GAMES, BANGKOK	GOLD MEDAL
1999-98	-	-	RAJIV GANDHI KHEL RATNA

1.2.2 HONOURED WITH AWARDS

AWARD NAME	RECEIPT YEAR	RECEIPT FIELD
ARJUNA AWARD	1995	TRACK AND FIELD
<u>RAJIV GANDHI KHEL RATNA</u>	1998-1999	TRACK AND FIELD
PADMA SHRI	2003	SPORTS

2. CONCLUSION

Among the many topics covered in the General Awareness section are sports-related awards and honours. Preparation for the general awareness domain is crucial. When it comes to general knowledge, static information is more significant than current events. Aspirants may choose to pass any competitive exam they take, provided they demonstrate a solid grasp of history, geography, science, the environment, and sports. "All work and no play make jack a dull boy" and "Practice makes a man great" are two classic proverbs that have a good impact on sports. During our time as students, we have all participated in athletic activities. Girls also showed interest in several sports, unlike the guys who were more likely to play indoor games like kabaddi, football, cricket, and other similar activities. Winners of athletic events may get trophies, banners, or even simply a participation certificate from their respective schools or colleges. In the realm of athletics, there are a handful of honours bestowed to participants at the public and state levels. Awards are given to all athletes by the central government of India and individual state governments. The Rajiv Gandhi Khel Ratna, Arjuna, Dronacharya, and Dyanchand prizes are among them. In 1946, under the auspices of Maharaja Yadvindra Singh, who was the

president of the Indian Olympic Association at the time, Prof. G.D. Sondhi was appointed as the inaugural president of the Apprentice Athletic Federation of India (AAFI). In 1946, the AAFI became a member of the International Amateur Athletic Federation. In any case, it adhered to the IOA's protocol for hosting the National Athletic Championship just once in

a span of two years. The decision to continuously conduct the National Athletic Championship was made by AAFI in 1949. Eight athletes, six men and two women, were surprisingly selected by the AAFI to participate in the 1948 London Olympics. For the first time since 1948, Indian women competed in the Olympics. Managing athletes, educating coaches, assembling a team of competent officials, bringing in international coaches to instruct Indian coaches and athletes, coordinating the visit of Olympic gold medalists to India for coaching and athlete control, and promoting sports In the lead-up to the Asian and Olympic Games, the Federation organised coaching camps for athletes, held clinics, and evaluated AAFI officials. The organization's dedication was on expanding the Open National Championship, presenting old enough group competitions, and

hosting zonal and interzone championships. From the Vedic era to the modern day, athletic sportsmanship has been highly regarded in India, and the country is actively involved in modern forms of athletics. Athletics in India have a long and storied history that begins with the Vedic period. Despite the fact that the exact moment when Indian athletics became a distinct sporting structure is a mystery, it is generally believed that the Atharva Vedic views formed the foundation of Indian athletics. An Indian politician and former athlete, Jyotirmoyee Sikdar was born on December 11, 1969. During the 14th Lok Sabha, she served as the Communist Party of India (Marxist)'s representative for the Krishnagar seat. Tapas Paul, a former comedian and current politician for the Trinamool Congress, defeated her in the 2009 Indian general election. It was said that after her destruction, she had remained politically dormant. She eventually pledged her support to the All India Trinamool Congress in 2019, and the following year she became a member of the Bharatiya Janata Party.

Gurudas and Nihar Sikdar of Debagram, Nadia locality, West Bengal, welcomed their son Sikdar into the world on December 11, 1969. She stayed focused all the way through high school. Sikdar wed Avtar Singh on February 9, 1994, and they have a son together.

As a former CPI(M) MP and Asian Games gold medalist Jyotirmoyee Sikdar became enamoured with Narendra Modi's Savka Saath Savka Vikash agenda, she joined the BJP in Kolkata. While receiving the saffron flag from West Bengal's president, Dilip Ghosh, 51-year-old Sikdar jumped at the chance to participate in Union Home Minister Amit Shah's virtual convention with the people of

West Bengal today. Having won multiple shrubs for India as a middle distance runner in the mid-1990s, including the Asian Athletics Championships and gold medals at the 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok, he transitioned into politics in 2004 and was elected to parliament from Krishnanagar on the Marxist ticket CPI(M). This is when she decisively defeated Satyabrata Mukherjee, a rising star in the BJP and the Union Minister of Chemicals and Fertilisers.

Subhas Chakraborty, a former sports serve, had a close relationship with Sikdar. As a member of the CPI (M) campaign, she was involved in the 2016 Assembly election. Regardless, the following 2009 parliamentary survey saw her defeated by the late Tapas Pal, a Tollywood star and relative unknown at the time.

She got political after her defeat and made a triumphant return in May 2019 when she became a member of the ruling Trinamool Congress. She went on to say that Chief Minister Mamata Banerjee's overall progress in Bengal had captivated her. However, she was likely waiting for the go-ahead when she hosted state BJP president Dilip Ghosh at her house last weekend and presented her with a pink lotus flower. (UNI)

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